

Cloud Computing and its Application in Nigerian Libraries: Challenges and the Way Forward

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Abstract

This paper is on cloud computing and the challenges to its application in libraries in Nigeria. The paper discussed the concept of cloud computing, the development and deployment of cloud computing, characteristics of cloud computing and types. The paper also discussed what to consider before implementing cloud computing, areas of application of cloud computing in libraries, and its benefits to libraries. Also, challenges to cloud computing application in libraries in Nigeria were discussed together with suggestions on how the identified challenges can be ameliorated. Some of the recommendations made are that: the nation's information and technology infrastructures and by extension, its Internet facilities should be improved upon from the present situation, solar energy should be explored as an alternative source of electricity power to replace the current unreliable power supply from the national electricity grid, among others.

Keywords: Application, Constraints, Cloud Computing, Libraries.

Introduction

The information environment in recent years has been changed by the convergence of ICTs such as computers, telecommunications, satellite broadcasting, and Internet technology. It is however the advent of the Internet that has so much impacted on the act of information dissemination in libraries and information centres around the world. The development of the Internet and other web enabled technologies on virtual platforms has helped to increase the opportunities for libraries and other similar organizations to use the services they provide for several purposes. Information flow and resource sharing has been also greatly enhanced by web technologies like 'cloud computing'. Cloud computing is the practice of using a network of remote servers hosted on the Internet to store, manage, and process data, rather than a local server or a personal computer. Library "users who have had the experience of using web 2.0 services like Wikipedia, blogs, and flickr etc; have already experienced cloud computing may be unknowingly" (Abidi and Abidi; 2012).

Today's "libraries have stepped up and are increasingly stepping into the realm of digital librarianship as well as platforms that extend IT's existing capabilities, and this extensively depends on using the cloud" (Movodza,2013).The use of cloud computing in education and other related areas of human endeavors is fast becoming very popular, and though cloud computing is a technology that has the potential of providing infrastructure and software solutions for the IT needs of libraries in Nigeria through the Internet, it is however only a few libraries that have adopted the technology (Seke,2015). Hence, the decision in this paper to consider cloud computing and the challenges of its application in libraries in Nigeria and proffer a way forward. This concept paper will provide an overview of cloud computing and its application in libraries in Nigeria. The paper also explored the various areas in the library's operations that cloud computing can be applied, the benefits of such application and the challenges associated with adopting cloud computing technology in Nigeria's libraries. The paper in conclusion also suggests ways the challenges identified can be minimized to enhance the use of the technology in libraries in Nigeria.

The Concept of Cloud Computing

The term "cloud computing" simply means "Internet computing". The Internet is metaphorically referred to as 'cloud' hence the term 'cloud computing' being used to denote computations carried out using the Internet. Users of cloud computing are able to access resources on data bases through the Internet from any location in the world and at any time they may need such resources without having to worry themselves about the problems associated with the maintenance or management of such resources (Wolf, 2010). Cloud computing combines the features of technologies like utility computing, unified computing, web 2.0, and the likes. The Garner Group (2009) defines cloud computing as "a style of computing in which massively scalable and elastic IT-enabled capabilities are delivered as service to external customers using Internet technologies". According to Kroski (2009) it "...means using web services for our computing needs which could include using software applications, storing data, accessing computing power, or using a platform to build applications". To the National Institute of Science and Technology (NIST,2012) cloud computing "...is a model for enabling convenient, on- demand network access to a shared pool

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of configurable computing resources (for ex, networks, servers, storage, applications and services) that can be rapidly provisioned and released with minimal management effort or service provider interaction”. On his part, Murky (2009), define cloud computing as “an emerging architecture by which data and applications dwell in cyberspace facilitating access to users through any web-connected device”. As Hoy (2012) further pointed out, “most cloud computing applications and infrastructures are built with the assumption that users will access them from the Internet, on multiple platforms and from any where in the world”. Cloud computing is nothing more than the collection of computing software and services that can be accessed via the Internet rather than residing on a desktop or internal server” (Stroh, Ache and Kumarl, 2009).

Figure 1: Shows a depiction of the Internet as a Cloud (Source: Yakubu, E.J; 2023)

Development and Deployment of Cloud Computing

How the term cloud computing originated is not clear, but the concept dates back to the 1960s, when John McCarthy first insinuated that “computation may someday be organized as a public utility” (wikipedia.org). It appears the term was derived from the practice of using drawings of stylized clouds to denote network in diagrams of computing and communication systems (Lewis, 2010). The cloud symbol was used to represent the Internet as early as 1994, but reference to cloud computing in the present sense was first made in 1996 in a Compaq internal document (Regalado,2001), and as computers became more popular, scientists and technologists explored ways to make large-scale computing power available to more users through time-sharing. What we know today as cloud computing is actually the result of the evolution and adoption of existing technologies and paradigms which allow users to take benefits from existing technologies without the need for deep knowledge about or expertise on any of them. The cloud aims to cut costs, and help the users focus on their core business instead of being impeded by IT obstacles (Hamdaqa, 2012).

Characteristics of Cloud Computing

The National Institute of Standards and Technology in Mell and Grance (2009) identifies five essential characteristics of cloud computing; these are:

1. **On demand self-service-** A consumer can unilaterally provision computing capabilities, such as server time and network storage, as needed automatically without requiring human interaction with each of the service provider.
2. **Broad network access-**capabilities are available over the network and accessed through standard mechanisms that promote use by heterogeneous thin and thick client platforms (e.g., mobile phones, tablets, laptops, and work stations).
3. **Resource pooling-** the provider’s computing resources are pooled to serve multiple consumers using multi-tenant model, with different physical and virtual resources dynamically assigned and reassigned according to consumer demands.

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4. **Rapid elasticity**- capabilities can be elastically provisioned and released, in some cases automatically to scale rapidly outward and inward commensurate with demand. To the consumer, the capabilities available for provisioning often appear unlimited and can be appropriated in any quantity at any time.
5. **Measured service**- cloud systems automatically control and optimize resource use by leveraging a metering capability at some level of abstraction appropriate to the type of service (e.g., storage, processing, bandwidth, and active user accounts). Resource usage can be monitored, controlled, and reported, providing transparency for both the provider and consumer of the utilized service.

Types of Cloud Computing and their Deployment in Libraries

Cloud computing is generally classified on the bases of services and usage.

Cloud Based on Services

- a. **Software as a service (SaaS)**- cloud providers install and operate application software in the cloud and users of cloud can access the software from cloud clients. The users are given access to application software and data bases online which they use without having to buy, install, run or maintain the software on their own servers. Since the cloud users do not manage the cloud infrastructure and platform on which the application is running, this then eliminates the need to install and run the application on the cloud user's own computers simplifying maintenance and support (Hamdaq, 2012). This service is used to provide email applications, free services, limitless storage, remote access from computers and devices that have Internet connection. Examples here include: Lib guides, salesforce.com, Google's Gmail and Apps, instant messaging from AOL, Yahoo and Google, also, VoIP from Vonage and Skype. These services (SaaS) are used in integrated library management and retrieval system for computing. The open-source software and open standards are also used for Internet based services towards next automated library system.
- b. **Infrastructure as a service (IaaS)**: This is the most basic cloud service model. In this service, a wide range of services, features and resources that can help in the building of a virtual infrastructure for computing are offered. Cloud providers offer these together with storages, networking and processing of data. They offer computers as physical or in most cases as virtual machines and other resources. The virtual machines are run as guests by a hypervisor, such as a Xen or XVM. Management of pools of hypervisors by the cloud operational support system leads to the ability to scale to support a large number of virtual machines (Amies, Sluiman, Tong and Liu, 2012). Vendors for IaaS are: Amazon.com for Elastic compute cloud (EC2) or simple storage service (S3), VMW, vCloud, IBM, Rack space, savvis, etc.
- c. **Platform as a service (PaaS)**: Here, cloud providers deliver a computing platform or application infrastructure which users require to build and run their web-based applications (soft wares and other tools) without managing the software and hardware. The user does not need to know programming language, database management systems and so on, to run the application, vendors of this service include: windows Azure, salesforce.com, ADP payroll processing, Google maps/ Google APP Engine etc.

What to Consider before Implementing Cloud Computing

When planning on applying cloud computing in the library, the following should be considered:

1. Who are the people that would be involved in the planning and preparation?
2. Deciding on compatibility of hardware and software to be used
3. Are software tools and other assistance available for the move?
4. What amount of data do you need to weed or convert to new format?
5. Who and how will the staff be trained once the new service is in place?
6. What new roles or tasks will IT cover?

Areas of Applying Cloud Computing in Libraries

As libraries try to make their services more accessible anywhere and at any time to users, they now deploy cloud computing services to achieve the goal. Cloud computing services and applications can be applied in libraries in the following areas:

1. **For file storage and preservation**- Using services such as Drop box, jungle Disk, Flickr, Google Doc, Sky Drive and the likes. Files can be stored, shared and accessed on the web from any place. Cloud based services like LOCKSS (Lots of copies keeps stuff safe), CLOCKSS (i.e. Controlled LOCKSS) and Portico tools are generally used to preserve digital documents in libraries.

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2. **For searching library Data base and for resource sharing-** The online computer library center catalogue (OCLC)'s Worldcat catalogue used for searching library data is presently available on the cloud. Through the OCLC Worldcat service, library services such as circulation, cataloguing, acquisition and so on, are provided on cloud via web share Management system that also facilitates the development of an open and collaborative platform which makes it easy for libraries to share their services, resources, ideas etc; with each other on the cloud.
3. **For setting up Digital libraries and repositories-** Every library needs a digital library through which it can make her resources and services accessible via the Internet, Duraspace has two software, namely Dspace and fedora commons. Fedora commons is the framework for digital repositories, while space is generally used for building digital libraries and repositories. Dura cloud which is closely related to Duraspace also provides open-source code needed to be installed on your libraries' machines. Duracloud provide storage and software you can use, and these you can subscribe to, if you want.
4. **For library Automation-** Polaris is a cloud-based library automation system which provides different types of cloud-based services for acquisition, cataloguing digital contents etc. The system uses a number of popular standards like, MARC 21, for bibliographic data, XML, Z39.50 for information retrieval, Unicode etc.
5. **For Hosting Library Websites-**Libraries may choose to host their websites on a third-party service provider's server instead of hosting them on their own servers. Website hosting was one of the earliest forms of cloud computing services provided. An example of a site hosting a library's servers which allows users to gain access from different locations on earth is Google sites.
6. **For scholarly content search-**The cloud-based platform that facilitates research and scholarly contents' sharing is Knimbus (Knowledge cloud). Knimbus is specifically designed and dedicated for knowledge discovery and collaboration among researchers and scholars. It enables them to discover and collaboratively share all kinds of knowledge.

Figure 2: shows the various areas of cloud computing application in libraries (Source: Yakubu, E.J, 2023)

Benefits of Adopting Cloud Computing in Libraries

Cloud computing has the following benefits when applied in libraries:

1. **Cost efficiency** –Using cloud computing helps the library to save costs in terms of extra charges on data storage, software updates, management and also reduces the cost of quality control.
2. **Low cost of maintenance-** Libraries does not have to pay any maintenance cost for hardware or software services provided to them by cloud providers. They only pay for resources used.
3. **Security-** Cloud services are made available to users 24/7 and as a result data centers go to great extent to ensure security and promote data integrity and confidentiality. Ordinarily, this will cost so much more if the library were to provide its own security.
4. **Provision of data back up and easy recovery-** A library that uses cloud services gets a safe back up for all her data and other documents. The recovery process for stored data in the cloud is very easy, fast and without much effort.

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5. **Unlimited storage capacity-** Cloud computing provides an unlimited amount of storage space for libraries. More data and documents can be stored in the cloud than on a library's machines, this eliminates the worry about the library running out of storage space on its machines or the need to upgrade such IT machines.
6. **Resiliency and redundancy-** In cloud computing, redundancy means that a duplicate copy of a document or data is available in the cloud, and a user who loses his or her data can always get a duplicate copy. The cloud is built on an architecture that is very robust and resilient hence providing resiliency and redundancy to its users. The resilience also includes disaster recovery services.
7. **Provide Easy Access to information and smaller learning curve-** the moment a user registers himself in the cloud, he gains access to information on the Internet from any part of the world. Cloud applications also provide smaller learning curves as people use them quietly.
8. **Users do not require any expertise-** The user does not need to master the application used in cloud computing to be able to use it. This means that anybody, with or without IT knowledge can use it (cloud computing).
9. **Quick deployment and ease of integration-** A cloud system can be deployed easily and kept running within a short period of time. A new user can be introduced directly to the system without their being required to wait for a period of time and this provide quick response to the end users.

Challenges Associated with the Adoption and Application of Cloud Computing in Libraries in Nigeria

In spite of the benefits that can be derived from applying cloud computing in libraries in Nigeria the following still remain issues that will need to be resolved:

1. **Internet bandwidth problem-** Deploying cloud computing require high bandwidth to enable usage. The Internet infrastructure in Nigeria is still relatively underdeveloped and there are no ways effective cloud computing services can be provided without high-capacity Internet bandwidth being available (Thomas, 2011; Suleiman, et al; 2017).
2. **Budget/funding constraints-** Money is required for subscription to cloud computing services and also to buy equipment required for setting up the service in libraries. The situation in most libraries in Nigeria is pathetic because they run their services on low budgets as a result of poor funding.
3. **Electricity/power supply issues-** Libraries need to provide Internet services 24/7 and without constant electricity/power supply this will not be possible and users' access to cloud services on the libraries' machines or on any other devices will be disrupted. Presently, electricity power supply in Nigeria is erratic and unstable (Suleiman, et al; 2017).
4. **Converting print documents to electronic ones-** Libraries' documents has to be in electronic formats for them to be made available on the cloud (Suleiman, et al; 2017). Most Libraries in Nigeria are yet to convert most of their documents like, theses and projects, and other documents to electronic formats, and this is a big issue.
5. **Lack of staff with technical knowledge and skills to provide I.T. Support in the area of maintenance and management of the library's end of the cloud services** (Suleiman, et al; 2017). This is a very important constraint in Nigeria.
6. **Security and privacy issues-** These are issues of major concern to libraries in Nigeria who want to use cloud computing services. The problem here involves unauthorized access to a library's data stored in the cloud. As different countries have different privacy requirements and standards, data stored on a cloud infrastructure hosted in a country where security and privacy laws are lax, can easily be compromised, thereby exposing such data to risk of a third party's unauthorized access (Thomas, 2011; Suleiman, et al; 2017). Nigeria at the moment lacks the capacity to provide cloud hosting infrastructures for her cloud users, all her cloud computing infrastructure needs are provided outside her shores by cloud companies she has no control over. The securities of the files are therefore in the hands of the company hosting them.

Conclusion

Cloud computing technology is fast becoming a necessity for libraries all over the world. As Lowry, Prudence, Karla and Stuart (2009) pointed out, "Libraries need to deliver services and resources to the virtual environments used by students, faculty and researchers or they risk alienating users". With cloud computing, libraries can meet all the information needs of different kinds of users, this is because with cloud computing, information is not stranded on individual machines, instead it is combined into one digital cloud and made available to users at the touch of a finger from many devices (Hamm, 2009).

Nigeria's libraries too can key into this all-important technology (cloud computing) so as to reap from the benefits it provides in today's twenty first century information environment.

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Recommendations for the Effective Application of Cloud Computing in Libraries in Nigeria.

To ensure the effective application of cloud computing in Nigeria's libraries, the following are recommended:

1. The nation's information and technology infrastructures and by extension, its Internet facilities will need to be improved upon. Internet services providers need to step up in this area, when this is done, as this will facilitate the provision of high-capacity Internet bandwidth that will run 24/7 in the nation's libraries thereby enhancing their ability to provide cloud computing services to their users.
2. Currently, almost all libraries in Nigeria are faced with funding problems. There is the need therefore for governments and other stakeholders at all levels to increase their funding to the libraries under their control because without money it will not be possible for these libraries to acquire the facilities and other equipments needed for providing cloud services. On their part, the libraries can source for funds from philanthropic organizations and individuals (like the MacArthur foundation and so on), to enable them acquire the facilities for setting up Internet and cloud computing services in their libraries.
3. Electricity power from solar energy can be used to replace or supplement the electricity supplied from the national grid which is currently erratic and unstable. This is necessary because to provide 24/7 cloud computing services, a stable power supply source is required.
4. Libraries in the country that want to extend the full benefits of cloud computing to their patrons, will have to ensure that their information materials like projects, and other documents are converted to electronic formats for easy upload to the cloud where patrons and other users can easily access them online through their computers and other devices.
5. Libraries require staff with skills in desktop and server operating systems administration, programming, data base management systems and network designs as well as in other Internet technologies to be able to implement cloud computing services effectively in the libraries. Aside employing staff with these IT know-how, the libraries must make training and re-training of its staff a priority for them to be able to keep up with the constant changes taking place in the field of library and information science technology.
6. Security and privacy issues which are often a major concern for libraries that wants to use cloud computing need to be addressed. The library in selecting a cloud hosting service provider may need to take into cognizance, the safety of its data when uploading them to the cloud. As a way of advice, libraries should not upload data or documents whose safety and security they are not sure would be guaranteed on the clouds.

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